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DiverIMPACTS

Diversification through Rotation, Intercropping, Multiple cropping, Promoted with Actors and value-Chains Towards Sustainability

Report:

Adoption of fair pricing relationships in different value chains. Analysis across DiverIMPACTS case studies.

WP contributions: WP5, WP2 and WP6.

Authors: Riera Anton (UCLouvain), Antier Clémentine (UCLouvain), Bliss Katie (ORC), Villa Abel (ORC).

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Contents

1. Introduction and objectives	5
1.1. Introduction.....	5
1.2. Objectives.....	5
2. Partners involved.....	5
3. Methodology and data	6
3.1. Methodology	6
3.2. Data.....	6
4. Results.....	7
4.1. Value-chain approach	7
4.2. Governance Mechanism.....	8
4.3. Consumer Engagement	9
4.4. Overall value chain development level.....	11
5. Discussion and conclusions	12
5.1. From fair prices to fair relationships.....	12
5.2. The path to adopting a fair relationships approach	13
6. References.....	17
7. Appendices.....	18

Executive summary

Fair pricing is a multi-actor question that requires a comprehensive analysis across all steps of a value chain, if the transition process towards diversified cropping systems is to be established and remain sustainable over time.

In consistency with initial research outputs of DiverIMPACTS, and on request of DiverIMPACTS partners, tools were developed by T5.3 to help case studies defining, assessing, and discussing the pricing in new, crop diversification based value chains. In particular, a list of 14 criteria relevant to define a "fair price" was elaborated (see D5.6). With that framework as a foundation, further analysis was undertaken by WP5, in collaboration with WP6 and with inputs from WP2, to assess the level of maturity of the DiverIMPACTS Case Studies value chains regarding fair pricing issues and fair relationships. In particular, three specific elements are looked at:

- **Value chain building and adoption of a “value-chain approach”:** The first aspects relates to the general approach of each case-study in terms of value chain building, i.e. what steps of the value chain are actively involved? Does the case-study only focus on technical aspects related to the production step or are partnerships with other actors pursued and established?
- **Governance models in place within the value chains:** The second criterion relates to the governance mechanisms which regulate each case-study. Are the value chains dominated by vertical relations with one major actor setting the rules? Or are the relations more horizontal with some degree of coordinated decision-making (e.g. through cooperatives)?
- **Consumer engagement:** As a “last step” in value chain building, this third criterion looks at how and to what extent each case-study engages and interacts with consumers. Are they actively involved in the value chain? Is the consumer’s perspective important and taken into account by the actors of the value chain? Or are these considerations not dealt with?

For each of these three elements, the DiverIMPACTS case studies are assessed with regards to which extent it is implemented, some case studies being more advanced than others. Indeed, in some cases, those elements are not discussed yet (*low implementation*); in some cases, they are discussed but not yet implemented (*medium implementation*); and finally, some cases are already implementing specific actions (*high implementation*).

Based on the implementation levels of the three studied aspects, we distinguish three levels of advancement of value chains: *Setting-up value chains - Enhancing value chains - Further developing value chains*. The analysis shows that among the analysed case studies, the majority of case studies

(18) have to some extent already engaged in fair pricing issues and implement concrete actions to work towards the development of fair value chains.

The analysis carried out above on the 25 DiverIMPACTS Case Studies confirms that the path towards *fair* value chains is not exempt of important challenges. By looking at how each case study implements three key aspects of *fairness within value chains*, the results suggest that some steps are easier to take than others. Indeed, the majority of analysed projects showcase a will to adopt a value chain approach, to engage with other actors and create lasting and fair relationships. However, implementing fair governance mechanisms and engaging with consumers appears as more challenging in practice. This could suggest that the adoption (or will to adopt) a value chain approach may appear as the first and easiest step to take in the process of building fair value chains. On the contrary, adopting fair governance mechanisms and engaging with consumers might come at ulterior steps, once the value chain and relationships among its actors are well-established.

1. Introduction and objectives

1.1. Introduction

The production and commercialisation of food products out of diversified cropping systems depend on actors' willingness to change and the availability of technical and organisational innovations, not only at the farm level but also at the storage, processing and retail levels. Additionally, further down the value chain, consumers also play a crucial role depending if they are interested in new products and are willing to pay what upstream actors charge for a product. In this context, fair pricing must thus be seen as a multi-actor question that requires a comprehensive analysis across all steps of a value chain if the transition process towards diversified cropping systems is to be established and remain sustainable over time.

1.2. Objectives

The objective of the hereby research is to analyse how different value chains apprehend fair pricing issues and, the level of advancement of their fair price strategies. Three aspects related to fair pricing are analysed before concluding on the overall adoption of fair pricing relationships within the Case Studies value chains.

2. Partners involved

This analysis was carried out as a collaboration between DiverIMPACTS Work Package (WP) 2, WP5 and WP6. The rationale of WP2 is to set up a case study network and approach for continuous innovation of crop diversification from a systemic 'transition' point of view and assess progress in both technological and institutional innovation. WP2's learning histories were precious to track the past and current state of fair pricing methods in Case Studies. WP5 aims to understand and overcome lock-ins at all levels of the value chain (farming systems, logistics, storage and processing, industry, retailers and consumers) and at different time and space scales (field, rotation, territory). The aim of WP6 is to develop, in a coordinated manner, strategies and recommendations to support innovations, cross-sectoral synergies, economic development, new business models and decision-making for increased crop diversification on each level of the value chain: food production, continued professional training, formal/academic education, regional management, consumer involvement, and policy and framework regulations on EU level (DiverIMPACTS DOA, p.38).

3. Methodology and data

3.1. Methodology

To achieve the above-mentioned objective, an analysis was done on the twenty-five DiverIMPACTS case studies. While fourteen fair pricing criteria have been identified in previous work carried out in the DiverIMPACTS project (Antier & Riera, 2022), three specific elements are studied in further detail, which allow to evaluate the adoption of a fair pricing approach through the entire value chain:

- **Value chain building and adoption of a “value-chain approach”:** The first aspect relates to the general approach of each case-study in terms of value chain building, i.e. which steps of the value chain are actively involved? Does the Case Study only focus on technical aspects related to the on-farm production or are partnerships with other actors pursued and established?
- **Governance models in place within the value chains:** The second aspect relates to the governance mechanisms which regulate each case-study. Are the value chains dominated by vertical relations with one major actor setting the rules? Or are the relations more horizontal with some degree of coordinated decision-making (e.g. through cooperatives)?
- **Consumer engagement:** As a “last step” in value chain building, this third criterion looks at how and to what extent each case-study engages and interacts with consumers. Are they actively involved in the value chain? Is the consumer’s perspective important and taken into account by the actors of the value chain? Or are these considerations not dealt with?

For each of these three elements, the DiverIMPACTS case studies are assessed with regards to their implementation of the aspect, some case studies being more advanced than others. In some cases, those elements are not discussed yet (*low implementation*); in some cases, they are discussed but not yet implemented (*medium implementation*); and finally, some cases are already implementing specific actions (*high implementation*).

Based on the combination of the implementation levels of the three studied criteria, we distinguish three types of value chains: *Setting-up value chains* - *Enhancing value chains* - *Further developing value chains*.

3.2. Data

This analysis was performed based existing data and results from the three involved WPs: WP2 (Colombo et al., 2020, 2021), WP5 (Antier & Riera, 2022; Morel, 2018) and WP6 (Villa, s. d.), which have been compiled in various DiverIMPACTS deliverables.

4. Results

This section presents the results of the assessment. Sections 4.1 to 4.3 first analyse the implementation of the three fair pricing aspects across the 25 DiverIMPACTS case studies. An overall evaluation of their value chain development stage is then presented in section 4.4. Results are summarised in Table 1 (condensed version) and Appendix

Table 2 in the Appendix (detailed version with short explanatory text).

4.1. Value-chain approach

Low implementation: Case studies with a low implementation of the value chain approach are characterised by an early organisation of production. In this stage, actors are organising activities to be carried out. These value chains are mainly centred on the production step, which involves farmers, technicians and researchers. These value chains are also working on complying with international and local guidelines. Within these guidelines are phytosanitary regulations for products as well as pest control inputs. In addition to this, actors are often working on creating knowledge and finding references for farmers. Farmers are working on treating the negative impacts of weeds and beetles on rape and knowing efficient farming practices from other farmers that have more experience in managing rape seed as a crop.

Medium implementation: Case studies with a medium implementation of the value chain approach are more organised in terms of production activities across the value chain, or at least they show a will to move towards the creation of coordinated and fair value chains. To this end, they may work on establishing and building relationships with other actors (which may be successful or not), or carry out market analyses to assess marketing possibilities. These case studies generally still work on developing knowledge on farming practices. Furthermore, in the specific context of crop diversification, it was reported that there is a general lack of cost-benefits assessment of introducing new crops and varieties from an environmental and economic perspective. Another important point related to the potential increase in management complexity of highly diversified vegetable systems, and the resulting increases in farmers' workloads.

High implementation: Case studies with a high implementation of the value chain approach have clear activities to carry out across the value chain. Relationships and partnerships between actors are well-established. Though knowledge remains an important asset to develop and improve current and future products, these cases are well embedded into diversifying cropping systems and developing products. This means that farmers and actors across the chain develop farming practices for managing

new crops in the local context, as well as integrating members of their communities and their contributions towards activities that support the value chain.

Analysis across DiverIMPACTS case studies: Overall, six case studies show a low implementation of a value chain approach, twelve case studies show a medium implementation and seven case studies show a high implementation (Figure 1). In general, this aspect is rather well implemented (it is the best implemented of the three aspects which are considered; see below). The majority of projects (76%) showcase some kind of value chain approach (medium or high implementation).

Figure 1. Analysis of DiverIMPACTS case studies (25) in terms of 'fair pricing' and 'fair relationships': implementation level of a value chain approach.

4.2. Governance Mechanism

Low implementation: Case studies with a low implementation of fair governance mechanisms characterise themselves by having decision making processes that are very vertical. In these cases, the value chains are organised and coordinated by a preponderant actor. This actor sets the activities and guidelines that other actors should follow. In this regard, price setting is regulated by what the preponderant actor indicates. In very few cases, farmers are creating an alternative approach for price setting. This can be achieved by creating alternative channels of distribution, for minor quantities which are sold on farms to regular customers.

Medium implementation: Case studies with a medium implementation of fair governance mechanisms characterise themselves by having decision-making processes that are more horizontal. Stakeholders at least initiate discussions to exchange on their respective challenges and enhance good communication. In some cases, the value chains are organised and coordinated by cooperatives. Though a cooperative can be considered a preponderant actor (on which farmers may be very dependent, as in CS14), the principle is to benefit all actors, especially the farmers that belong to it. The cooperatives organise the activities that the other actors should follow. Price setting results from

channels of negotiations (the coop buys the product from the farmer and then sells it). Finally, in some cases, farmers may also look for alternative selling channels to keep a certain degree of freedom.

High implementation: Finally, case studies with a high implementation of fair governance mechanisms showcase similar decision-making processes as enhancing value chains. However, the distinction between the two resides in the level of involvement and communication of actors across the value chain and, in a couple of cases, the involvement of consumers as well as citizens (see also criteria 3). In terms of price setting, the organisation and coordination is led by one of the actors in the value chain with the acknowledgement of the rest of the actors all along the value chain. Therefore, prices are discussed commonly and price setting involves the participation of all the actors in the chain, including consumers in some cases. Actors are well-aware of their production costs, which are taken into account in the price setting mechanisms. In some cases, premiums or contracts are put in place.

Analysis across DiverIMPACTS case studies: Overall, ten case studies show a low implementation of a value chain approach; eleven case studies show a medium implementation and only four case studies show a high implementation (Figure 2). Although the majority of case studies (60%) undertake some actions related to fair governance mechanisms (medium or high implementation), a significant share of case studies (40%) show low implementation.

Figure 2. Analysis of DiverIMPACTS case studies (25) in terms of ‘fair pricing’ and ‘fair relationships’: implementation level of fair governance mechanisms.

4.3. Consumer Engagement

Low implementation: Case studies in this situation do not actively pursue consumer engagement. They reach out and engage with consumers indirectly, based on activities to stabilise production. For example, in order to create a presence with consumers, the strategy begins with managing production on a yearly basis, to be marketed locally. In other value chain cases, engaging with consumers is through intermediaries. Twelve case studies fall in this situation.

Medium implementation: Case studies in this situation recognise and acknowledge the necessity to engage and account for consumers, although active engagement is not always carried out yet at present (but remains a pursued target). Possible strategies which are considered by case studies to achieve this mainly include consumer surveys and the dissemination of information.

High implementation: Case studies with a high level of consumer engagement are at a stage where specific activities are put in place to reach out to consumers (rather than just acknowledging the importance of it). Engaging with consumers implies embedding the value chain into the local communities. In these cases, actors carry out all activities from upstream to downstream. This may include the development of consumer surveys or the assessment of consumers' willingness to pay. The use of labels can also be a means to achieve consumer engagement. Additionally, this integration also enables the use of the farm as a means to reach consumers, for example by organising events and other dissemination activities (film screenings, producing articles, etc.). To reach out to consumers in the nearby communities, some value chains implement programmes involving community representatives.

For example, in one of the Cases, this consists of loyal consumers who are knowledgeable about the sustainable farming practices and see value in consuming and supporting farmers that carry out these activities. These representatives sell vegetables box schemes in their respective communities and, by word of mouth, they increase the customer base. In another Case, the consumer strategy consists in reaching out to professional chefs, school canteens and online shops. In this particular case the processor is the actor that coordinates the strategy. A professional chef is part of the actors of the value chain. The chef organises workshops with other chefs working at restaurants. With this strategy, the aim is to show and teach how to cook lupin and prepare different dishes with it. In addition to this, the value chain targets school canteens to teach young children and teenagers how to enjoy lupin and other pulses in different dishes. This creates a future customer base that will potentially demand this type of products. As a matter of fact, the processors has noticed a growing demand, from teenagers in particular, for vegan and vegetarian dishes, in which lupin can be used as a substitute for meat.

Analysis across DiverIMPACTS case studies: Overall, eleven case studies show a low implementation of consumer engagement, ten case studies show a medium implementation and four case studies show a high implementation (Figure 3). Among the analysed case studies, this criterion seems to be the most difficult to implement. Indeed, although a slight majority of projects (56%) acknowledge the importance or undertake some kind of consumer engagement (medium or high implementation), almost half of case studies (44%) show low implementation.

Consumer engagement

Figure 3. Analysis of DiverIMPACTS case studies (25) in terms of ‘fair pricing’ and ‘fair relationships’: implementation level of consumer engagement.

4.4. Overall value chain development level

Fair price strategies in value chains differ as a result of the type of value chain and its local context. Based on the level of implementation of the three criteria which were analysed above, we assess the overall stage of development of each case study in terms of fair pricing relationships. We identify three main stages of value chain development: *setting up value chains*, *enhancing value chains* and *further developing value chains*.

- **Setting up value chains** are value chains which are in the early stages of development. This means that from upstream to downstream, actors, their activities, as well as their relationships are being organised.
- **Enhancing value chains** are value chains with intermediate levels of development. This means that from upstream to downstream, actors and their activities have established relationships and collaborations across the chain. As a result, the value chain produces a product with attributes, but still needs to develop further strategies to scale up.
- **Further developing value chains** are value chains which are already developed in terms of activities and relationships across actors and stages. This means that across the value chain actors already have clear activities to conduct and additionally there is co-creation of knowledge. Furthermore, there is involvement from the community, the value chain is embedded in finding attributes to the products.

Analysis across DiverIMPACTS case studies: Overall, seven case studies can be classified as *setting up value chains*, twelve case studies are classified as *enhancing value chains* and six case studies are classified as *further developing value chains* (Figure 4). These results show that, among the analysed

case studies, the majority of case studies (18) have to some extent already engaged in fair pricing issues and implement concrete actions to work towards the development of fair value chains.

Figure 4. Analysis of DiverIMPACTS case studies in terms of 'fair pricing' and 'fair relationships': implementation level of three criteria and assessment of overall value chain development stage.

Note: The overall stage of development (*setting up – enhancing – further developing*) is determined as a result of the individual implementation levels of the three criteria (*value chain approach – fair governance – consumer engagement*).

5. Discussion and conclusions

5.1. From fair prices to fair relationships

An important comment regarding the issue of fair pricing relates to the scope of the question. Indeed, the analysis carried out above proposes to look at the question from a wide perspective, not only in terms of fair *prices* but rather in terms of fair *relationships* within the value chain. Indeed, the three aspects analyzed in this report look at the adoption of a *value chain approach* (crit. 1), the adoption of *fair governance mechanisms* (crit. 2) and the *engagement with consumers* (crit. 3). While the question of prices can be approached through each of these criteria, their objective is to account for other important aspects.

For example, aspect 1 (adoption of a value chain approach) can be useful to the question of pricing through the benchmarking exercises and comparison with reference market prices. However, this element is also about building up relationships with other value chain actors. Similarly, aspect 2 can relate to prices through questions on price setting mechanisms and who sets the price within the value

chain. However, it is also about the overall communication and transparency within the value chain, and the general decision-making processes that are adopted (not only for questions of prices). Finally, regarding aspect 3 (consumer engagement), the acceptability of the price by consumers obviously plays an important role (which can be estimated through consumer surveys, etc.). Yet, this aspect is also about the wider engagement with consumers, for example through communication, dissemination of information or the organisation of events and field visits, the use of labels, etc. In some case this can go until the inclusion of consumers in the decision-making processes.

Innovative ways to set prices, and thereby achieve *fair* prices, are necessary. This will in many cases include a necessary calculation of production costs. Other possible options are setting a minimum price, the adoption of a price premiums for farmers (such as in case study 15 in the UK; see Table 2), including consumers in the price setting mechanisms (such as in the *C'est qui le patron*¹ brand in France), etc. Yet, it is important to acknowledge that additional aspects related to specific context of a value chain can also infer on the fairness of a price. For example, local conditions in terms of access to land or the social status of consumers will in many cases highlight the fact that fair prices are highly context-specific. While two situations might share the same technical production conditions, the local context might mean that a price considered as fair in one situation is not fair in the other (Garbarczyk & Vanwelde, 2018). Hence, accounting for interpersonal relations, fostering communication and creating a sense of shared purpose among actors of a value chain are crucial issues, equally important to the monetary aspects of price, to achieve overall fairness in a value chain.

5.2. The path to adopting a fair relationships approach

The analysis carried out above on the 25 DiverIMPACTS Case Studies confirms that the path towards *fair* value chains is not exempt of important challenges. By looking at how each case study implements three key aspects of *fairness within value chains*, the results suggest that some steps are easier to take than others. Indeed, the majority of analysed projects showcase a will to adopt a value chain approach, to engage with other actors and create lasting and fair relationships. However, implementing fair governance mechanisms and engaging with consumers appears as more challenging in practice. This could suggest that the adoption (or will to adopt) a value chain approach may appear as the first and easiest step to take in the process of building fair value chains. On the contrary, adopting fair

¹ [C'est qui le patron](#) is a brand launched in 2016 in France in which consumers are involved in the price setting mechanisms (e.g. by evaluating their willingness to pay) with the aim of providing a fair price for producers. It started with milk and now includes about 30 products.

governance mechanisms and engaging with consumers might come at ulterior steps, once the value chain and relationships among its actors are well-established.

Table 1. Analysis of DiverIMPACTS case studies in terms of ‘fair pricing’ and ‘fair relationships’: implementation level of three elements characterizing the level of advancement of *fair relationships* and resulting overall assessment stage.

Case Study ID			Value chain approach	Fair governance mechanisms	Consumer engagement	Stage of Development
#	Origin	Name				
1	NL	New crops (sorghum) and intercropping in dairy maize monoculture	Low	Low	Low	Setting up value chain
2	UK	Mix varieties of plants in leys (valorised through livestock) to break arable rotations	Low-Med	Low	Med	Setting up value chain
3	DE	Service crops as additional catch crops (multiple cropping), cover crops and undersown grasses as intercropping to improve water quality	Low-Med	Low	Low	Setting up value chain
4	BE	More diverse leys (more species and varieties, complex mixes) as winter cover crops grazed by sheep on arable farms	Med	Low-Med	Low-Med	Enhancing value chain
5	FR	Longer rotations to break maize monoculture (e.g. soybean)	Low-Med	Low	Low	Setting up value chain
6	CH	Oilseed rape and other oils (pumpkin, gold of pleasure, flax, hemp etc.)	Med	Med	Med	Enhancing value chain
7	HU	Soybean in cereal-based rotations	Med	Med	Low	Enhancing value chain
8	RO	Dry legumes for food (e.g. chickpeas, lens), legumes for feed (peas, clover, soybeans, alfalfa, lupine), legumes in winter cover crops	Med	Med	Low-Med	Enhancing value chain
9	IT	Diversification of durum wheat cropping systems in semi-arid environment with sulla and other crops (chick pea and hemp)	Med-High	Low	Med	Enhancing value chain
10	PL	Oilseed rape, flax, milk thistle (<i>Silybum marianum</i>) for oil	Low-Med	Low	Low	Setting up value chain
11	FR	Protein crops for feeding (local) livestock	Low-Med	Low-Med	Low	Setting up value chain

12	BE	Various diversification practices to combine conservation agriculture and organic farming	Low	Low	Low	Setting up value chain
13	FR	Legume-brassica mixtures as service crops and for biomass	Med	Med	Med	Enhancing value chain
14	FR	Longer rotations and pea-wheat intercropping; niche crops (e.g chickpea, coriander, sorghum) reinforcing minor crops (sunflower, lentil, pea)	Med	Med	Low	Enhancing value chain
15	UK	Pulses and alternative crops (quinoa, buckwheat)	High	High	Med-High	Further developing value chain
16	NL	Strip cropping for grain, legume and vegetable crops	Med	Low-Med	Med	Enhancing value chain
17	BE	Pea-wheat intercrop	Med-High	Med	Med-High	Further developing value chain
18	BE	Minor crops in general (e.g quinoa, millet, lentil, cameline)	High	High	Med	Further developing value chain
19	SE	Legume crops (lupine, lentil, pea, fava bean, phaseolus)	Med-High	High	High	Further developing value chain
20	CH	Lupine for food and soybean for feed	High	Med	Low	Further developing value chain
21	BE	Land exchange for grass-clover in vegetable rotations and vegetables in grassland rotation	High	High	Med	Further developing value chain
22	IT	Minor crops, land races (wheat, legumes, vegetables); strip cropping	Med	Med	Med	Enhancing value chain
23	NL	Improving efficiency of vegetable systems to keep them diversified	Med	Med	Med	Enhancing value chain
24	UK	High diversity of vegetable species and varieties in rotations, intercropping, green manures, cover crops	Med	Med	High	Enhancing value chain
25	FR	Keeping existing diversity of vegetables	Med	Med	Low	Enhancing value chain

Authors: Anton Riera, Abel Villa.

6. References

Antier, C., & Riera, A. (2022). *Tools for defining a fair price and strengthening crop diversification value chains*. DiverIMPACTS Practice Abstract.

Colombo, L., Gomiero, T., Cuijpers, Y., de Jong, D., Gorissen, L., Leclère, M., & Rossing, W. (2020). Mid-term CSs' evolutions in terms of quantitative and qualitative indicators. *DiverIMPACTS Deliverable 2.3*, 177.

Colombo, L., Vanhove, P., Curran, M. P., Bliss, K., Villa, A., Dumper-Pollard, R., Cuijpers, Y., de Jong, D., Gorissen, L., & Rossing, W. (2021). Second intermediate report on CSs' evolutions in terms of quantitative and qualitative indicators. *DiverIMPACTS Deliverable 2.4*, 113.

Garbarczyk, B., & Vanwelde, M. (2018). *Le prix juste. Et si on prenait le problème à la racine ?* Solidarité des Alternatives Wallonnes et Bruxelloises (SAW-B).

Morel, K. (2018). Ordered list of lock-ins for CSs. *DiverIMPACTS Deliverable 5.1*.

Villa, A. (s. d.). Regional Management and Consumer strategy. *DiverIMPACTS WP6 - T6.4*.

7. Appendix

Table 2. Analysis of DiverIMPACTS case studies in terms of ‘fair pricing’ and ‘fair relations’: implementation level of three criteria and assessment of overall value chain development stage (detailed).

Case Study ID			Value chain approach	Adoption of fair governance Mechanisms	Consumer engagement	Stage of Development
#	Origin	Name				
1	NL	New crops (sorghum) and intercropping in dairy maize monoculture	Low Issue only approached from technical/production perspective, with technicians and researchers.	Low Not applicable in this CS as it is centred on production/technical aspects.	Low Not considered.	SETTING UP VALUE CHAIN
2	UK	Mix varieties of plants in leys (valorised through livestock) to break arable rotations Service	Low-Med The economic impacts of herbal leys at farm-level are considered but no real value chains are being built up.	Low Not applicable in this CS as it is centred on production/technical aspects.	Med Market opportunities for grass-fed livestock are considered through a consumer survey.	SETTING UP VALUE CHAIN
3	DE	Service crops as additional catch crops (multiple cropping), cover crops and undersown grasses as intercropping to improve water quality	Low-med No real value-chains are being set-up, but the CS acknowledges that it has to create a broader visibility in the region (in terms of engagement of actors).	Low Not applicable in this CS as it is centred on production/technical aspects.	Low Not considered.	SETTING UP VALUE CHAIN

4	BE	More diverse leys (more species and varieties, complex mixes) as winter cover crops grazed by sheep on arable farms	<p>Medium</p> <p>The CS mainly includes farmers but relationships with financial organisations and local authorities are established too. (web platform to enhance partnerships)</p>	<p>Low-Med</p> <p>No real considerations related to price setting but the CS aims to get staff support to facilitate governance and operational aspects.</p>	<p>Low-Med</p> <p>No real consumer engagement but dissemination actions are undertaken (film screening, articles, etc.)</p>	ENHANCING VALUE CHAIN
5	FR	Longer rotations to break maize monoculture (soybean is an example)	<p>Low-med</p> <p>Mainly focuses on technical and economic aspects. The CS also aimed to identify stakeholders by analysing the agro-food chain.</p>	<p>Low</p> <p>Not applicable in this CS as it is mainly centred on production/technical aspects.</p>	<p>Low</p> <p>Not considered.</p>	SETTING UP VALUE CHAIN
6	CH	Oilseed rape and other oils (pumpkin, gold of pleasure, flax, hemp etc.)	<p>Med</p> <p>Meetings are held with a farmers' association (Fenaco) in order to establish relations; contacts taken with retailers (but did not work out).</p>	<p>Med</p> <p>Stakeholders discuss their commitment and ideas. But the price is probably still set by the main actor.</p>	<p>Med</p> <p>The CS is looking for additional farmers willing to sell oil directly to consumers.</p>	ENHANCING VALUE CHAIN

7	HU	Soybean in cereal-based rotations	<p>Med</p> <p>Value chain building is slow but the CS tries to identify and meet with potential value chain stakeholders, to stimulate cooperation between actors (including seed companies and material producers).</p>	<p>Med</p> <p>Farmers are waiting for good market conditions, which could be provided by the processors, but the processors are also waiting for the organic soybean production to reach a stable and big acreage.</p> <p>Some farmers have created alternative ways of marketing their products allowing them to set their prices.</p>	<p>Low</p> <p>Not considered (yet ?).</p>	ENHANCING VALUE CHAIN
8	RO	Dry legumes for food (e.g. chickpeas, lens), legumes for feed (peas, clover, soybeans, alfalfa, lupine), legumes in winter cover crops	<p>Med</p> <p>Market opportunities are explored.</p>	<p>Med</p> <p>Farmers want to keep flexibility and sell where the highest prices are.</p>	<p>Low-Med</p> <p>Large farmers feel they are too far away from consumers to develop niche markets.</p>	ENHANCING VALUE CHAIN
9	IT	Diversification of durum wheat cropping systems in semi-arid environment with sulla and other crops(chick pea and hemp)	<p>Med-High</p> <p>An operational group is set up. Relationships are established with various organisations (local authorities, etc.). Additional in-depth market studies may offer new insights that would orient business opportunities and strategies.</p>	<p>Low</p> <p>Prices and quality criteria are fixed by agroindustry and farmers have not much to say about it. Lack of cooperation among farmers to bargain with agroindustry, leading to unbalanced power between farmers and contractors, processors. Farmers are completely dependent.</p>	<p>Med</p> <p>Possibility to organise panel tests to see if the end products meet the consumers appreciation of novel products.</p>	ENHANCING VALUE CHAIN

10	PL	Oilseed rape, flax, milk thistle (Silybum marianum) for oil	<p>Low-med</p> <p>There is a general lack of trust between farmers and the CS concludes that the market and policy do not provide stability and sustainability for diversified systems. A contract with the biggest petrol retailer in Poland (ORLEN) has allowed the CS to enter a new and promising market.</p>	<p>Low</p> <p>Each year, farmers are dependent on new contracts and new requirements.</p>	<p>Low</p> <p>Not considered?</p>	<p>SETTING UP VALUE CHAIN</p>
11	FR	Protein crops for feeding (local) livestock	<p>Low-med</p> <p>Workshops are organised to bring farmers and local actors together but low levels of participation of farmers.</p> <p>Surveys and interviews are performed to research the technical and economic indicators for the farmers, and social indicators to better understand the obstacles and motivations to the practice of exchanges.</p>	<p>Low-Med</p> <p>Lack of long-term arrangements with guaranteed prices and specified quality (secure outlet). Risky for farmers as arrangements are for one year and prices are not guaranteed (soybean prices can change a lot).</p> <p>Need of arrangements allowing to overcome fiscal barriers to sell products between farmers.</p>	<p>Low</p> <p>Not considered?</p>	<p>SETTING UP VALUE CHAIN</p>

12	BE	Various diversification practices to combine conservation agriculture and organic farming	<p>Low</p> <p>Focus is set on technical aspects.</p>	<p>Low</p> <p>Lack of trust in knowledge exchanges and competition on markets. Every farmer has his own market, commercial relationships and arrangements with buyers and is quite secret about it. No collective action to put pressure on research institutions or collectors.</p>	<p>Low</p> <p>Not considered?</p>	SETTING UP VALUE CHAIN
13	FR	Legume-brassicacee mixtures as service crops and for biomass	<p>Med</p> <p>Intervention and market options are explored (interviews with economic SHs and farmer leaders). Many niche markets seem already occupied.</p> <p>Setup of a platform providing agronomic and economic figures ; successes and setbacks.</p>	<p>Med</p> <p>Presence of a cooperative.</p>	<p>Med</p> <p>Considering to assess willingness to pay by consumers for cosystemic services linked to diversification (e.g. Carbon storage with service crops) as these are not well known or visible to them.</p>	ENHANCING VALUE CHAIN

14	FR	Longer rotations and pea-wheat intercropping; niche crops (e.g chickpea, coriander, sorghum) reinforcing minor crops (sunflower, lentil, pea)	<p>Med</p> <p>Discussions around value chain aspects exist (among others, presence of a cooperative).</p> <p>For new crops, balance between offer and demand has been looked at to keep high prices.</p>	<p>Med</p> <p>contracts are individually negotiated between farmers and their clients.</p> <p>The bargaining power of farmers with cooperatives looks limited. Farmers rely strongly on cooperatives to tell them what they should grow or not.</p>	<p>Low</p> <p>Not considered?</p>	ENHANCING VALUE CHAIN
15	UK	Pulses and alternative crops (quinoa, buckwheat)	<p>High</p> <p>Various actors are involved, with a lot of knowledge exchange between actors.</p>	<p>High</p> <p>An added value calculator is used; a price premium is put in place; a workload and quality of life survey is carried out.</p>	<p>Med-High</p> <p>Aim to enhance consumer engagement (e.g. through social media).</p>	FURTHER DEVELOPING VALUE CHAIN
16	NL	Strip cropping for grain, legume and vegetable crops	<p>Med</p> <p>The CS has engaged with various actors (local authorities).</p> <p>The CS has studied the supply chain and marketing possibilities for strip cropping products.</p> <p>Involving commercial advisors is regarded as tricky.</p>	<p>Low-Med</p> <p>Individual support of farmers is depending on a few individuals right now.</p>	<p>Med</p> <p>The CS acknowledges the need to investigate how strip cropping could be valued by consumers and citizens</p>	ENHANCING VALUE CHAIN

17	BE	Pea-wheat intercrop	<p>Med-High</p> <p>Relationships are established with several actors along the value chain (Walagri, AVEVE, Cosucra, local authorities).</p> <p>A higher valorisation of the wheat was proposed to the farmers, allowing for a higher income.</p> <p>Market analyses are performed.</p>	<p>Med</p> <p>Lack of contracts guaranteeing a better traceability without increasing costs too much</p>	<p>Med-High</p> <p>The CS has identified the need of communicating about ecosystemic services and making consumers pay for it but this can be challenging with several intermediaries.</p> <p>The use of labels is considered.</p> <p>A programme is developed to communicate and raise further awareness among industry and consumers on the pea+wheat.</p>	FURTHER DEVELOPING VALUE CHAIN
18	BE	Minor crops in general (e.g quinoa, millet, lentil, cameline).	<p>High</p> <p>Farmers, processors and retailers come together and communicate.</p>	<p>High</p> <p>Prices are set collectively, taking (among others) production costs into account.</p>	<p>Med</p> <p>Uncertainties about the possibility for customers to accept more variable products from more artisanal and local processing.</p>	FURTHER DEVELOPING VALUE CHAIN

19	SE	Legume crops (lupine, lentil, pea, fava bean, phaseolus bean).	<p>Med-High</p> <p>A network of the CS was established with several stakeholders (including contacts with local authorities). A common plan across the value chain was established.</p> <p>Although some potential demand already exists, there are still few value chain actors and marketing outlets for Swedish legume crops in Sweden.</p>	<p>High</p> <p>3-5 years contracts with secured quantities and prices</p> <p>CS actors exchange and communicate to understand respective wishes and fears; challenges and bottlenecks.</p>	<p>High</p> <p>Consumer engagement is pursued through mass media attention, webpage, local radio, films, articles, TV reportages...</p>	FURTHER DEVELOPING VALUE CHAIN
20	CH	Lupine for food and soybean for feed	<p>High</p> <p>Relationships are established with various actors along the value chain (retailer, processor).</p> <p>Market analyses are carried out.</p>	<p>Med</p> <p>No long-term perspective and communication between actors on the development of a market for food lupine/soybean in Switzerland. No long-term contracts for organic protein crops. Farmers are not sure about quantities processors can buy and processors are not sure about quantities farmers can produce.</p>	<p>Low</p> <p>Not considered?</p>	FURTHER DEVELOPING VALUE CHAIN

21	BE	Land exchange for grass-clover in vegetable rotations and vegetables in grassland rotation	<p>High</p> <p>Cooperation between plant & animal producers, who come together.</p> <p>No actual value chain building as vg and livestock producers are involved in separate value chains.</p>	<p>High</p> <p>The value and price of grass clover are discussed between actors.</p> <p>Actors discuss mutual needs; finding common issues; discussing financial opportunities. Compromises are reached when some partners feel unsatisfied.</p>	<p>Med</p> <p>Necessity to communicate and engage with consumers is acknowledged but considered complicated as the subject is complex.</p>	FURTHER DEVELOPING VALUE
22	IT	Minor crops, land races (wheat, legumes, vegetables); strip cropping	<p>Med</p> <p>Actions to build a value chain are undertaken (meeting with local stakeholders involved in tourism and catering).</p> <p>A value chain stakeholder engagement plan was established.</p>	<p>Med</p> <p>seem to rely importantly on CS leader (a partner left due to a change in CS leader)</p>	<p>Med</p> <p>Communicating about the benefits of diversification is perceived as a big challenge. This is pursued through online and offline communication, and involvement of tourism agencies.</p>	ENHANCING VALUE CHAIN
23	NL	Improving efficiency of vegetable systems to keep them diversified	<p>Med</p> <p>Mainly involves farmers</p>	<p>Med</p> <p>Mainly based on knowledge exchange.</p>	<p>Med</p> <p>The CS targets local supply chains and the possibilities of a webshop as an alternative marketing channel.</p>	ENHANCING VALUE CHAIN

24	UK	High diversity of vegetable species and varieties in rotations, intercropping, green manures, cover crops	<p>Med</p> <p>The CS is looking to establish relationships with a wide range of actors along the value chain, including consumers, food system actors, seed producers, nature organisations and researchers.</p>	<p>Med</p> <p>A survey was conducted among value chain partners, combining qualitative and quantitative questions exploring the impact of crop diversification on various social / personal health elements of the farm business.</p>	<p>High</p> <p>Consumer engagement is actively pursued. An online survey with consumers was conducted.</p>	<p>ENHANCING VALUE CHAIN</p>
25	FR	Keeping existing diversity of vegetables	<p>Med</p> <p>The CS carried out an economic evaluation of diversified systems. Marketing issues are discussed.</p>	<p>Med</p> <p>Competition has historically been important in the area, leading to a general 'individualism' which complicates collaboration.</p> <p>Lack of formalised and long-term coordination.</p> <p>Unequal relationships between actors in long supply-chains. Marketers do not necessarily respect their informal engagements. For processors, it is difficult to secure and plan supply because transformation is seen by farmers as a last resort solution as it does not bring much added value for farmers; new types of contracts may help.</p>	<p>Low</p> <p>Not considered?</p>	<p>ENHANCING VALUE CHAIN</p>

